

Some signatures of large distant information teleportation between cellular DNAs in biological wires

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Abstract: Biological cells like plant cells could communicate with other distant cells even through some layers of glass. These cells could emit some waves which force into micro-organisms, oil and water bubbles to form some electrical wires. This is because that these micro-organisms and bubbles are formed from charged particles and by their motions, some waves are emerged. These waves could be taken by other DNAs. For example, cellular DNAs emit some waves and these waves are taken by some micro-organism's DNAs and in response, these genetic matters force to the micro-organisms to become parallel or anti-parallel or even perpendicular to the cellular DNA waves. The same may be occurred for oil and water bubbles. These bubbles are surrounded by charged particles and could take cellular DNA waves and become parallel or anti-parallel to them. Consequently, some micro-organisms and bubbles join to each other and form electrical wires. These wires could act like metal wires; however with biological properties and emit some electromagnetic waves. These waves could pass the glass and some other types of matters and give the biological information to target cells. To form these wires, metals could be useful. Micro-organisms and charged bubbles usually attach to a metal and form several linear wires near it. Because, metals have minor currents which emit some electromagnetic waves and absorb micro-organism's DNAs and charged bubbles. Among different metals, a combination of aluminum/silver-polycarbonate could work better. This system could have two sides, one reflecting side which reflect light and other non-reflecting side. Reflecting side produces wires with light dark color and non-reflecting side produces wire with white/yellow color. Copper wires also produce bacterial lines which become curve near the end of wire. This is because that at the end of copper wires, magnetic fields become curve and bacteria will be arranged in parallel magnetic waves.

Keywords: Biological Wires; Distant Information Teleportation; Plant cells; Metals; DNA waves

I. Introduction

Up to date, it has been known that some types of biological objects like cells, bacteria, viruses and micro-organisms could exchange electromagnetic waves and interact with each other and any external wave. For example, a group have put two vessels including liquids and bacterial/viral DNAs within a coil and emit some electromagnetic waves. They have shown that bacterial DNAs interact with these external waves and exchange some frequency of waves with each other [1,2]. Another group have tried to find a bridge between waves, water molecules, plant cells and bacteria. They have shown that waves originating from a strong pulsed electric field could transmit molecule information into water and have great effects on bacteria and plants [3]. Other team have proposed some methods to consider the effects of low frequency electromagnetic waves on the bacterial evolutions. They have shown that these waves cause to a decrease in growth rate and morphological changes for both Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria [4]. Another investigators have studied the effects of millimeter waves on *Escherichia coli* and many other bacteria and discussed that these waves lead to a significant change in bacterial activity and growth rate [5]. Other scientists have considered the physical properties and the behavior of a type of bacteria called magnetotactic bacteria (MTB). These bacteria have the unique ability to produce magnetic particles surrounded by a biomembrane to form the magnetosome organelle [6,7]. Besides the bacteria, chloroplasts also have their own genetic matters like DNAs and could send or take electromagnetic waves. Chloroplasts play a central role in plant defense and are targeted by pathogen effectors [8]. They may interact with each other and bacteria and control infectious diseases. Considering exchanged waves between chloroplasts and bacteria could help us to understand bioelectrical engineering of cells [9]. On the other hand, some investigations show that some biological particles could form a wire and allow for long distance electron transport between electron donors to electron acceptors [10-12]. Motivated by

these researches, we propose a method to build some biological wires/antenna and transmit information from a biological system in one side of a glass to a complete separate distant system in other side of that glass. We also discuss about the role of metals in biological information teleportation between two separate cells or biological wires.

II. Material and Method:

Material:

1. Leaf
2. Micro-organisms like Bacteria/plastids/water/oil
3. Several glass slides
4. A combination of aluminum/silver or other types of metal-polycarbonate
5. Copper wire
6. Ice-water
7. Camera
8. Light Microscope

Method:

1. First, we design a slide with the genus of metal-polycarbonate and provide a hole in it (Slide 1).
2. We divide the leaf into two parts. We put one part under a glass slide and another part on the upper of it and in a separated distance from first part.
3. We put several ice under the slide and cool it.
4. Then, we put this system under a microscope.
5. We change the place of lenses and take photos of both two slides. DNAs of plant cells are formed from charged particles and by their motions within the cells, some waves are emerged. DNA waves interact with micro-organism's DNAs and force them to become parallel or anti-parallel or even perpendicular respect to the emitted waves (See figure 1).
6. We replace the metal-polycarbonate slide by glass one and repeat previous stages.

7. We divide the metal-polycarbonate slide into several parts and put some parts on the upper and lower slide such as the reflecting parts and non-reflecting parts and non-reflecting part become distributed. Metal systems have some minor currents which emit electromagnetic waves and absorb micro-organisms like bacterial DNA inductors. This causes to formation of biological wires along metals (See figure 2).
8. We remove metal-polycarbonates totally and put several copper wires on the upper and lower slides (Slide 2).

Fig 1: A designed slide for considering distant information teleportation between plant cells and micro-organisms like bacterial and bubble wires

Fig 2: Application of metal wires in distant information teleportation between plant cells

Results:

1. On the upper slide, some biological lines were formed. These lines began from the leaf part towards another leaf part (See figure 3).
2. Some of elements of these biological lines were big and some were small (See Figure 4).
3. These lines may form from water/oil bubbles, bacteria and other micro-organisms (See figures 1-7)
4. These lines may be ended to second part of leaf (See figure 5).
5. Biological lines/wire are usually in parallel to each other (See figures 6 and 7)
6. Near the walls of metal-polycarbonate systems, micro-organisms form wires or parallel lines (See figure 8).

7. On the upper slide and other side of glass respect to metal-polycarbonate system, biological lines are perpendicular respect to the slide wall (See figure 9).
8. The reflected parts of metal-polycarbonate system could produce dark biological lines through the glass and on the other/upper side of slide (See figure 10).
9. The non-reflected part of metal-polycarbonate system could produce light biological lines through the glass and on the other/upper side of slide (See figure 11).
10. Two parallel copper wires, one on the above side and other under the glass and separated from initial one could increase density of micro-organisms (See figures 12 and 13).
11. Micro-organisms on the second side of a glass could interact with copper wire on the first side (See figure 14).
12. Micro-organisms at the end of wire form several magnetic curves respect to wire (See figure 14).

Fig 3: Formation of biological wires for a part of leaf during interaction between two separate leaves (First picture)

Fig 4: Formation of biological wires for a part of leaf during interaction between two separate leaves (Second picture)

Fig 5: Formation of biological wires for a part of leaf during interaction between two separate leaves (Third picture)

Fig 6: Formation of biological wires for a part of leaf during interaction between two separate leaves (Forth picture)

Fig 7: Interaction between biological wires on the upper side of a slide and plant cells on the down side of a slide

Fig 8: Formation of biological wires through absorption of micro-organisms and charged bubbles by the metal-polycarbonate system

Fig 9: Interaction between biological wires on the upper side and non-reflecting part of metal-polycarbonate system in down side of a slide (glass)

Fig 10: Interaction between biological wires on the upper side and reflecting part of metal-polycarbonate system in the down side of a slide (glass)

Fig 11: Formation of ordered triangular shape of biological wires on the upper side of an slide and a triangular metal-polycarbonate on the down side

Fig 12: micro-organism and charged bubble density near a copper wire in interacting with second copper wire (First Picture)

Fig 13: micro-organism and charged bubble density near a copper wire in interacting with second copper wire (Second Picture)

Fig 14: Formation of micro-organism curves near the end of a copper wire

Discussion:

Above results show that

1. Plant cells could communicate with other distant plant cells and exchange some waves.
2. These waves may be originated from evolutions of their DNAs. Because, DNAs are formed from charged particles and by their motions within cells, some waves are radiated.
3. These waves force into water/oil molecules, charged bubbles, micro-organisms like plastids and bacteria to form some wires and lines. Because, micro-organisms have their own DNAs which could receive DNA waves of cells and become parallel or anti-parallel or perpendicular respect to them. Also, oil and water bubbles are formed from charged particles and interact with waves.
4. Some elements or bubbles of these biological wires are more bigger and some are smaller. Big bubbles are closed to cells and by going distance, bubbles become smaller.
5. These biological wires could interact with cells and other wires even through glass slides.
6. Metallic systems and wires could help in formation of biological lines/wires.
7. A combination of some metals like Aluminum or silver with polycarbonates could be more effective respect to copper wires.
8. We can use of biological wires in large distant information teleportation in future.

Conclusion:

In this research, we have shown that plant cells could exchange waves with each other. These waves interact with micro-organisms, water/oil and charged bubbles and force them to stand in several lines. This is because that membranes and also, DNAs of biological particles are formed from charged particles and could act like the receiver or sender of waves. Microbial and bubble wires could interact with each other and send some waves. These waves could be taken by biological wires in separate distant or even on other side of glass and transmit to other cells. Some metals like aluminum and silver could absorb micro-organisms and charged bubbles and help in formation of biological wires. Also, copper wires play the main role in attracting some

micro-organisms and formation of wires. Density of micro-organisms becomes more near the ends of metals and some magnetic curves are formed.

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